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Seating Arrangement and Academic Performance of Bachelor of Elementary Education Students

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between seating arrangement and academic performance among Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) students at Eastern Samar State University - Guiuan Campus. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study aims to explore natural associations between seating configurations and academic outcomes, utilizing a survey questionnaire adapted from previous research. Data collection involved administering the questionnaire to 121 BEED students across different academic levels. Statistical analysis, including frequency counts, percentages, and the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, was employed to interpret the data. Findings indicate that students perceive seating arrangements as influential on their academic engagement and performance, particularly highlighting psychological comfort as a significant factor. Results from the survey reveal an overall positive perception towards seating arrangements, with most students agreeing on the effectiveness of their current seating setups. Academic performance, measured through General Weighted Average (GWA), shows a majority of students achieving proficient and very good ratings. Statistical analysis confirms a moderate correlation ($r = 0.498$, $p = 0.059$) between seating arrangement and academic performance, suggesting a significant relationship. This implies that while seating arrangement is not the sole determinant of academic success, it plays a noteworthy role in student outcomes. In conclusion, the study underscores the importance of considering seating arrangements in enhancing classroom dynamics and improving educational outcomes. It provides valuable insights for educators and educational policymakers to optimize learning environments. Recommendations include empowering students in seat choice, designing learner-centered seating plans, and enhancing school infrastructure to foster conducive learning environments. Future research directions are proposed to further explore experimental approaches and refine strategies for improving learning quality and processes.

Keywords: *performance, students, arrangement, academic*

Introduction

Classroom seating arrangements are, undoubtedly, a crucial element in establishing the physical classroom environment (Corkin, Horn, & Pattison, 2017). When classroom seating arrangements are thoughtfully organized by teachers into logical, methodical structures that facilitate student learning and complement the teacher's teaching style, they can significantly enhance the learning experience. However, problems can arise when teachers do not choose their seating arrangements carefully and meaningfully (O'Hare, 2016). A classroom's seating arrangement can influence students' perceptions of the class, often recalling past experiences with similar setups (Jones, 2019).

If a student has had an unpleasant experience in a classroom or with a specific content area linked to certain seating arrangements, it could lead to considerable angst towards the classroom, the subject, and the teacher (Dykman & Reis, 2014). Therefore, seating arrangements must be effective, logical, and purpose-driven to facilitate the subject matter being taught.

This works under the proposition that some seating arrangements are more effective than others (McCorskey & McVetta, 1978). In other words, certain seating arrangements can hinder a teacher's efforts to establish rules, standards, and regulations from the first day that persist throughout the school term.

The effectiveness of classroom seating arrangements is a measurable, observable phenomenon, influenced by various factors including the teacher's teaching style, class size, and other elements of the physical classroom that are beyond control, such as the location of doors and windows, the teacher's desk, built-in or freestanding bookshelves, and the placement and size of chalkboards or whiteboards (Cooperative Research Program, 1965).

Locally, the researcher will conduct a study on the effectiveness of seating arrangements in relation to BEED students' academic performance at ESSU - Guiuan. The purpose of this study is to demonstrate, through measurable student-specific data, that certain classroom seating arrangements are indeed more effective. It will examine how different seating locations and arrangements impact students' academic performance, based on the observation that seating arrangement is a key strategy for managing learners. This study could also guide future researchers in understanding how to manage classroom settings and apply these learnings in practice.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of seating arrangements on the academic performance of BEED students at ESSU - Guiuan during the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

- 1.1. seating arrangement; and
- 1.2. academic performance?
2. Is there an influence of seating arrangement on students' academic performance?
3. What recommendations can be offered based on the study?

Literature Review

According to Corkin, Horn, and Pattison (2017), classroom seating arrangements play a pivotal role in shaping the learning environment and influencing academic outcomes. Their study highlighted that well-organized seating structures can foster a sense of community among students and enhance overall academic performance. Conversely, poorly chosen arrangements may lead to distractions and hinder effective learning interactions.

McCorskey and McVetta (1978) explored the dynamics between instructional communication theory and student preferences in seating arrangements. They found that aligning classroom setups with student preferences can positively impact engagement and participation, ultimately affecting academic success. This suggests that understanding student preferences and integrating them into seating strategies could be crucial for optimizing learning environments.

O'Hare (2016) investigated the relationship between classroom design, including seating arrangements, and student engagement. The study emphasized that strategic placement of students can influence their level of involvement in classroom activities and interactions with peers and instructors. Effective seating designs were shown to enhance student focus and participation, thereby contributing to improved academic performance.

Harvey and Kenyon (2014) examined student preferences regarding various seating arrangements. Their findings indicated that flexible seating options, such as movable chairs and group-oriented setups, were favored by students due to their facilitation of collaborative learning and active participation. Such preferences underscore the potential benefits of adaptable seating configurations in promoting academic engagement among elementary education students.

Rands and Gansemer-Topf (2017) discussed how physical classroom environments, including seating arrangements, can impact student engagement and learning outcomes. Their research highlighted that well-designed classroom spaces that accommodate diverse learning needs and encourage student interaction contribute significantly to academic achievement. This suggests that optimizing seating arrangements could be a strategic approach to enhancing educational outcomes in elementary education settings.

Insights into Classroom Seating: This article emphasizes the role of seating arrangements in shaping students' cognitive performance. It suggests that strategic seating can enhance learning experiences and outcomes by facilitating better peer interaction and teacher accessibility.

Classroom Climate and Academic Performance: A study from De La Salle University highlights a low positive correlation between classroom climate, including seating arrangements, and academic performance among education students. The study suggests that while the correlation is present, it explains only a small variance in academic performance.

Students' Preferences for Seating Arrangements and Engagement: Research indicates that students' seating preferences can significantly impact their engagement levels. Preferred seating arrangements often lead to higher attentiveness and participation, which are critical for academic success.

Differential Effects of Seating Arrangements: This source discusses how different seating arrangements (traditional rows vs. more interactive setups) influence student interactions and academic outcomes. It highlights that seating arrangements can affect not only academic performance but also social dynamics in the classroom. (www.dlsu.edu.ph)

The classroom environment plays a crucial role in student learning, with the seating arrangement being a key component. How students are seated can significantly influence their engagement, collaboration, and overall academic performance. Understanding the impact of seating arrangements on learning can help educators create more effective classroom environments that enhance both teaching and learning experiences (Hudson, 2024). The arrangement of seating in a classroom can impact students' psychological and cognitive processes by reducing distractions and improving focus. In primary schools, flexible seating arrangements are particularly beneficial as they accommodate developmental needs, maintaining attention and improving learning outcomes. Social dynamics within the classroom are also affected by seating arrangements, with configurations like circular seating promoting interaction and traditional rows limiting it.

Research indicates that flexible seating plans, which allow for movement and choice, increase student engagement and motivation. Different seating arrangements, such as rows, clusters, U-shaped, and flexible seating, have varying effects on student learning. Factors like the teacher's role, student preferences, and the nature of classroom activities mediate the relationship between seating arrangements and learning outcomes. Each seating arrangement has unique advantages and disadvantages, impacting both teaching and learning dynamics. Effective seating arrangements consider student needs, promote collaboration, minimize distractions, and balance different seating options. By designing effective seating arrangements and managing classroom dynamics proactively, educators can create a positive and conducive learning environment where students can thrive (Hudson, 2024).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to investigate the relationship between seating arrangement and academic performance of BEED students at Eastern Samar State University - Guiuan Campus.

Descriptive-correlational research aims to determine the extent of relationships between variables. It describes variables and examines the natural associations between them (Burns & Grove, 2015). This design is particularly suitable when experiments are impractical or unethical, allowing for the exploration of associations among variables (Davis et al., 2021).

Creswell (2018) defines correlational research as a method to clarify associations among variables at a specific point in time. It is a quantitative approach that explores relationships between two or more quantitative variables within the same group of subjects (Waters, 2021).

Respondents

The respondents for this study will be the BEED students of Eastern Samar State University - Guiuan Campus. They will include students enrolled in the academic year 2023-2024. To gather the profile of the respondents, a standard survey questionnaire will be administered to collect relevant data.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

<i>Eastern Samar State University – Guiuan Campus</i>	<i>Number of BEED students/respondents</i>
BEED IV	36
BEED III	36
BEED II	49
Total	121

Instrument

The researchers used a survey questionnaire to gather data from the BEED students of Eastern Samar State University - Guiuan Campus. The questionnaire was adapted from Angela Jean Hammang's instrument and modified to suit the objectives of the study.

The survey questionnaire was designed to capture the respondents' profiles in terms of how seating arrangements impacted their academic performance. It consisted of 35 items, each rated on a 4-point ordinal scale numbered 1 to 4, with descriptions ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree."

The first part of the instruments is about seating arrangement with three indicators based on the study about "The Effects of Seating Assignment on Student Achievement in Biology Classroom" by Angela Jean Hammang. The second part is the pupils' Point Grade Average. The survey questionnaire is answerable by encircling the ordinal rating scale numbered 1 to 5 with description of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree in ascending manner.

Procedure

The researchers administered the survey questionnaires to the BEED students of Eastern Samar State University - Guiuan Campus. Prior to conducting the study, written permission was obtained from the university authorities. Once approved, the questionnaire was distributed to the respondents. The students were given sufficient time to carefully complete the survey questionnaire.

After collecting the survey instruments, the researchers reviewed each questionnaire to ensure all items had been adequately answered. They also observed how teachers engaged students in seating arrangements that may influence academic performance.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis will be the most precise and objective step in analyzing the result of the study. Simple frequency counts, percentages, rating and means will be employed to present the profile of the respondents in terms of seating arrangement and academic performance.

In determining the relationship between seating arrangement and academic performance, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient Formula will be use being the most appropriate statistical tool.

The following alternative hypothesis will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

There is significant relationship between seating arrangement and academic performance.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings that address the research questions posed in this study based on the data gathered from BEED students

at Eastern Samar State University - Guiuan Campus.

Profile Of Respondents On Seating Arrangement

This section addresses the first research question regarding the profile of respondents in terms of the influence of seating arrangements. Table 2 presents the respondents' perceptions towards classroom arrangements. The table includes 35 items which were rated by the BEED students of Eastern Samar State University - Guiuan Campus.

Specifically, the table displays indicators/items on the perception of seating arrangements' influence, along with their corresponding mean scores, scales, interpretations, overall mean, and grand total mean as perceived by the students.

Table 2 summarizes the data for three indicators related to seating arrangements. For the first indicator, which focused on physical factors, the data revealed that the respondents perceived these factors as effective, with an overall mean score of 2.69 and an interpretation of "Agree". Notably, question number 12, "I like the door open during class", received the highest mean score of 3.66, indicating strong agreement and high effectiveness in this aspect.

Regarding the second indicator, which examined social factors, the respondents agreed that these factors influence seating arrangements, with an overall mean score of 2.79 and an interpretation of "Agree". Question number 24, "I am more likely to raise my hand if I sit in the front", received the highest mean score of 3.72, indicating strong agreement and high effectiveness.

Highlighting the third indicator, psychological factors, the respondents perceived these factors as highly effective in influencing seating arrangements, with an overall mean score of 3.20 and an interpretation of "Agree". Question number 40, "My teacher tries hard to make class a good learning experience for me to listen attentively and participate in class", received the highest mean score of 4.00, indicating strong agreement and maximum effectiveness.

Overall Perception on Seating Arrangement

Assessing the impact of seating arrangements on the learning process, Table 2 reveals an overall mean score of 2.99 across three indicators, with an interpretation of "Agree." This result underscores the significant role that seating arrangements play in influencing the learning outcomes of BEED students at Eastern Samar State University - Guiuan Campus. The data indicates that students perceive seating arrangements as an important factor that affects their engagement, participation, and overall academic performance.

The study's findings highlight the importance of considering seating arrangements as a key component in classroom management and instructional strategies. By understanding how different seating configurations affect students' learning experiences, educators can make informed decisions to enhance classroom dynamics and improve educational outcomes. This awareness can lead to the implementation of seating strategies that foster a more conducive learning environment, ultimately benefiting student engagement and achievement.

Table 2. *Perception of Respondents on Seating Arrangement*

<i>Indicators/ Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Scale</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Physical factors			
1. I am most comfortable sitting in the middle of the class.	3.45	Strongly Agree	Highly Effective
2. When facing the board, I prefer to sit on the left side of the classroom	2.72	Agree	Effective
3. I have hard time seeing the chalkboard or smart board when the teacher is writing on the board.	2.74	Agree	Effective
4. When facing the board, I prefer to sit on the right side of the class.	2.81	Agree	Effective
5. I like to sit by the back door of the classroom.	2.12	Disagree	Less Effective
6. I have hard time hearing if I sit at the back of the classroom.	2.60	Agree	Effective
7. I am more likely to raise my hand if I sit in the back.	3.18	Agree	Effective
8. I am most comfortable sitting near the front in the classroom.	3.31	Strongly Agree	Highly Effective
9. I am more likely to raise my hand if I sit in the front of the class.	3.61	Strongly Agree	Highly Effective
10. I like to sit close to the door in my classes.	1.96	Disagree	Less Effective
11. I am more comfortable sitting in the back of the class.	2.54	Agree	Effective
12. I like the door open during the class	3.66	Strongly Agree	Highly Effective
13. I sit in different location in my classes.	2.31	Disagree	Less Effective
Overall Mean	2.69	Agree	Effective
Social factors			
14. I prefer to work with others.	3.42	Strongly Agree	Highly Effective
15. I like to sit away from my teacher.	2.42	Disagree	Less Effective
16. I sit away from people who appeared to be sick.	2.85	Agree	Effective
17. Most of my teacher assign seats in their classroom.	3.61	Strongly Agree	Highly Effective
18. I like to sit near my teacher.	3.18	Agree	Effective
19. I do better when I sit next to my friend.	3.19	Agree	Effective
20. I prefer sitting by girls in class.	2.97	Agree	Effective
21. I do not sit by boys in class.	2.59	Agree	Effective
22. I am unaffected by the student that mess around in class all the time.	2.85	Agree	Effective

23. I prefer sitting by boys in class.	2.84	Agree	Effective
24. I am more likely to raise my hand if I sit the front of the class.	3.72	Strongly Agree	Highly Effective
25. I feel like I get in people's way when I sit in the front.	2.85	Agree	Effective
Overall Mean	2.79		
Psychological factors			
26. I prefer to work by myself.	2.97	Agree	Effective
27. I prefer picking my seatmate.	2.95	Agree	Effective
28. If given a choice I would sit in the same seat all year long.	2.97	Agree	Effective
29. I like to choose my own seat in class.	2.94		
30. If given a choice, I would change my seat in class often.	2.45	Disagree	Effective
31. I tend to be talkative if I am near my friends during class because it lessens my attention towards the topic.	2.48	Disagree	Less Effective
32. Sitting away from students that do not stay on task makes me more productive.	3.22	Agree	Less Effective
33. I like it when my teacher assigns group activities because it motivates me to cooperate	3.74	Strongly Agree	Effective
34. I like when my teacher chooses my seat in front because it makes me feel like a vital part of the class	3.55	Strongly Agree	Highly Effective
35. My teacher tries hard to make class a good learning experience for me to listen attentively and participate in the class.	4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Effective
Overall Mean	3.13	Agree	

Legend: 3.26 - 4.00, Strongly Agree/Highly Effective; 2.51 - 3.25, Agree/Effective; 1.76 - 2.50, Disagree/Less Effective; 1.00 - 1.75, Strongly Disagree/Not Effective

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents according to Seating Arrangements

Category	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	Highly Effective	2	2%
Agree	Effective	107	88%
Disagree	Less Effective	12	10%
Strongly Disagree	Not Effective		0%
Total		121	100%

Table 3 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of seating arrangement, using scales, interpretations, frequencies, and percentages. The scale of "Agree" had the highest frequency count of 107, indicating a significant number of students felt positively about their seating arrangements. Following this, the scale of "Disagree" had 12 counts, showing a smaller portion of students did not find the seating arrangements favorable. The "Strongly Agree" scale had a low frequency count of 2, while the "Strongly Disagree" scale had no frequency counts at all, totaling 121 frequency counts.

These results suggest that the majority of BEED students at Eastern Samar State University - Guiuan Campus are generally satisfied with their seating arrangements, as evidenced by the high frequency of agreement. The negligible counts for "Strongly Agree" and "Strongly Disagree" indicate that extreme opinions on either end of the spectrum are uncommon among the respondents. This distribution highlights a general consensus towards the effectiveness of current seating arrangements, with few students feeling strongly negative or exceptionally positive.

Figure 1. Profile of Respondents in terms of Seating Arrangements

The graph above represents the profile of the BEED students in ESSU - Guiuan in terms of seating arrangement. The graph shows the percentages and interpretations of the respondents in terms of seating arrangement. From the given data, we could infer that the physical,

social, and psychological factors of the respondents are effective in choosing seating arrangement.

Based on the conduct survey it was implied that the percentage of 88% out of 121 total number of respondents, suggested that they were effective, second was 10% responded less effective, 2% of the respondents perceived that they were highly effective seating arrangements and 0% of the respondents perceived that they were less effective and not effective seating arrangements.

Profile of the Respondents on Academic Performance

This section answered the questions regarding the profile of the respondents in terms of academic performance. Table 4 shows the respondents’ profile in terms of General Weighted Average (GWA) with their corresponding mean average, scale and interpretation as perceived by the respondents.

As shown in the table, the highest average is 1.7 with a scale of advanced and was interpreted as outstanding. The second highest is 1.6 with a scale of advanced and was also interpreted as outstanding. It means that the pupils are doing well with their studies influenced with their seating arrangement.

On the other hand, it was revealed that the lowest average is 2.7 with a scale of developing and was interpreted as fair. Which only means that some pupils are still aiming to be on top. Their performance is on the process of improvement, hence they are doing just enough to meet the passing grade.

Table 4. Perception on Academic Performance

GPA	Mean	Scale	Interpretation
	1.81	Proficient	Very Good

Overall Perception on Academic Performance

As shown in table 4, the grade point average got an overall mean score of 1.81 with a scale of proficient and was interpreted as very good. It means the pupils meet the passing grade. Thus, it is well understood that all of the pupils are excellent with their performances.

Table 5. Profile of the respondents on academic performance

Scale	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
Advanced	Outstanding	19	15.44%
Proficient	Very Good	46	38.23%
Approaching Proficiency	Good	35	29.41%
Developing	Fair	21	16.91%
Beginning	Poor	0	0
Total		121	100%

As shown in the table 5, this was the distribution of respondents according to academic performance, the highest frequency counts was on the scale of proficient with a frequency of 46. The second highest was on the approaching proficiency with a frequency counts of 35, followed by the scale of developing with a frequency counts of 21. The lowest was on the scale of beginning with no frequency counts and this gives a total of 121 counts

Figure 2. Profile of Student's Academic Performance

The above figure represents the profile of respondents in terms of academic performance. As observed in the figure above, they have used the interpretation of the means score in the table 4 to completely discuss the distribution of the respondents according to the second variable. This implied that 38.23% of the 121 total numbers of the respondents were very good in their studies, 15.44% of the respondents were outstanding in terms of academic performance and 16.91% are doing fair in school.

Relationship between Seating arrangement and Academic Performance

In order to answer the question on the relationship between variables, the “Pearson’s R Correlation, Coefficient was employed as a statistical test to gain much reliable and valid result.

Table 6 shows the variables correlated with one another together with their corresponding coefficient, p-value, and their respective interpretation.

Table 6. *Correlation between Seating Arrangement and Academic Performance*

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Interpretation
Seating arrangement	Academic Performance	0.498	Moderate Correlation	0.059	Significant

The relationship between seating arrangement and academic performance was shown in Table 6. The computed r value was 0.498 which was acceptable relationship. This resulted in a p-value of 0.59 which was at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis that seating arrangement significantly influence academic performance among pupils was accepted.

Based from the gathered data, it was revealed that seating arrangement has something to do of pupil’s academic performance in the classroom. Indeed seating arrangement can be a great help for the better performance of learners and promote better attitude towards learning.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, positive insights were drawn regarding the influence of seating arrangements on students’ academic performance. The gathered, analyzed, and interpreted data clearly indicated that the respondents’ academic performance is affected by their seating arrangements. The study identified three key indicators of seating arrangement: physical, social, and psychological, with psychological factors standing out as the most influential. This suggests that a well-thought-out seating arrangement, particularly one that considers psychological comfort, can lead to better academic performance.

Furthermore, the correlation analysis revealed a moderate relationship between seating arrangements and pupils’ academic performance, underscoring a significant link between the two variables. This moderate correlation implies that while seating arrangement is not the sole factor affecting academic performance, it is a noteworthy contributor. The overall results of this study provide valuable insights for the Program Head, faculty members, and stakeholders of Eastern Samar State University - Guiuan Campus. Understanding the impact of seating arrangements can guide the implementation of strategies to optimize classroom environments, thereby enhancing students’ academic outcomes.

Based on the findings and conclusions that were drawn, the following recommendations were made:

For the students, so they may choose to sit where they feel not only comfortable but also where they can become more confident, attentive, participative, productive and can hence improve their academic performance.

For the faculty members, so they may take into consideration the maximum learning of their pupils thru creating a learner –centered seating plan that can encourage participation amongst students when necessary and by not only focusing on trying to discipline misbehaved pupils thru seating arrangements that would otherwise discourage pupils from communicating with classmates during class discussions.

For Educational Managers / Program Heads / In - Charge, so they may impose seating arrangements that works best for the improvement of academic performance of their students. This study aims to help School Heads in choosing the most appropriate seating arrangement for a wide variety of learners.

For Schools and other academic institutions in general, so that they may provide the necessary equipment and infrastructure that would give a more conducive learning environment for the learners.

For future researchers who wish to conduct an experimental research about seating arrangement –this study will take them halfway across the journey. And for other future researches that aims to improve the quality of learning and the learning process.

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